

COMMENTARY

This paper is responding to an article published in the European Journal of Soil Science by Berthelin et al. (2022)

NEW FINDINGS...

Berthelin et al. (2022) claim that, for the first time, they closely examine the short-term breakdown process of fresh organic materials added to soil, which they believe has been mentioned in past literature but not studied extensively

...OR OLD NEWS?

Angers and colleagues disagree and argue that we've already known for nearly a century that when organic carbon is added to the soil, most of it doesn't stay there forever. A significant part is lost to the atmosphere in form of greenhouse gases

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14974471](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14974471)

AUTHORS

Angers Denis, Dominique Arrouays, ...
Johan Six (2022)

A WELL-ESTABLISHED FACT: CARBON TURNOVER IN SOIL IS NOT A ONE-WAY STREET

Part of the carbon cycle

When organic matter is introduced to soils, a part of its carbon is stored whereas another part is respired by microbes and lost to the atmosphere.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

This project has received funding by EU H2020 European Joint programme EJP SOIL (grant agreement no. 869625).

PROGRAMME COORDINATOR:

Claire Chenu

ejpsoilcoord@inrae.fr

TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Understanding how soil-carbon sequestration can contribute to **climate change mitigation** at the regional level and **accounting for carbon**.

Mission SOIL: conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL
framework programme

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

EJP SOIL has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme: Grant
agreement No 862695

